

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B270
Date: 24 February 2007
Take Off 08:55:19
Landing: 14:44:33
Flight Time 5h49m14

Campaign: GFDEX - Targeted observations of SAP south of Iceland)

Operating Area: Iceland Coast (Targ Obs)

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Ian Renfrew	UEA
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics / Core Chem	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
7	AVAPS	Stuart Heath	FAAM
8	Mission Scientist 2	Emma Irvine	Reading University
9	Mission Scientist 3	Dave Sproson	UEA
10	Mission Scientist 4	Shunli Zhang	University of Toronto
11	Mission Scientist 5	Margaret Munro	University of Toronto
12			
13			
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Flight Track:

B270 Track 24-FEB-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b270
 Date: 24/2/07
 Project: GFDEX
 Location: SW of Iceland - SAP

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
084010		engine start	0.30 kft	248	
084121		inu to nav	0.30 kft	248	
084315		taxy	0.30 kft	248	
085519		T/O	0.31 kft	001	from Keflavik
085908		asp open	7.4 kft	088	
092014		Sonde 1	24.0 kft	090	
092317	102852	Run 1	24.0 kft	193	
094213		bbr	24.0 kft	179	extend
094355		Sonde 2	24.0 kft	178	
094536		Contrails	24.0 kft	180	intermittent
100649		Sonde 3	24.0 kft	181	
103007		Sonde 4	24.0 kft	281	
103519	105406	Run 2	25.0 kft	273	
105515	114203	Run 3	25.0 kft	004	
105515		Sonde 5			
111846		Sonde 6	25.0 kft	358	
114203		Sonde 7	25.0 kft	359	
114357	121326	Run 4	26.1 - 26.0 kft	320	
121517	132330	Run 5	26.0 kft	183	
121517		Sonde 8			
123842		Sonde 9	26.0 kft	181	
130150		Sonde 10	26.0 kft	183	
132330		Sonde 11			
144433		Land	0.26 kft	003	at Keflavik
145039		standstill	0.25 kft	244	63'59.66, 22'37.65

B270 Track 24-FEB-07

GFDex Sortie Brief – B270 – 24 February 2007

Targeted observations of Sensitive Area Prediction south of Iceland (Plan 104)

Mission Scientists: Ian R, Emma Irvine, Dave Sproson, Shunli Zhang, Margaret Munro

Aims

- Dropsonde observations of areas of forecast sensitivity in the vicinity of Iceland
- High-level (25-30 kft) legs in lawnmower pattern with dropsondes released every 120 nm
- Verification areas: NWEU (North West Europe) primarily, some SCAN sensitivity too.
- Optimisation times: 36-48 hours; VT 00z and 12z 26 February
- Missions can be flown at **most efficient speed**

GFD104	Time	Manoeuvre	Distance (nm)	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1	0900	Take off Keflavík , transit to 64N, 18W.	120		
2		Straight level run at 25-30 kft, due south to 58N, 18W. All legs at most efficient speed Dropsonde releases every 120 nm (4 in total).	360		
3		High-level leg due west (heading 270°) to 58N, 22W	127		
4		Straight level run at 25-30 kft, due north to 62N, 22W Dropsonde releases every 120 nm (3 in total).	240		
5		High-level leg to 64N, 26W	162		
6		Straight level run at 25-30 kft, due south to 58N, 26W. Dropsonde releases every 120 nm (4 in total). If not enough fuel, cut this leg at 60N, 26W.	360		
7		Transit to Keflavík.	374		

Mission Scientists Debriefing Sheet

Flight No. **B270**

Targeted observations of Sensitive Area Prediction south of Iceland (Plan 104)

Date: **24 February 2007**

Aims

- Dropsonde observations of areas of forecast sensitivity in the vicinity of Iceland
- High-level (25-30 kft) legs in lawnmower pattern with dropsondes released every 120 nm
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Assessment of the Flight

Highly successful.

All 11 dropsondes worked well, apart from drop 4 which did not start receiving wind data till 580 mb (whereas T etc was 440mb). All dropsondes were transmitted onto the GTS in real time, and all made the Met Office database in time for the 12 UTC forecast, i.e. made the QG cycle. Modification to dropsonde launch system has allowed wind data to be received immediately upon launch – an excellent initiative by Stuart Heath.

Realised during flight that a zig-zig pattern northbound would have saved around 30 minutes flying time; such patterns will be used in the future.

Summary of weather conditions

Low pressure system over British Isles, SE flow over flight area. Generally cloudy.

Ian Renfrew

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.270** Date **24 Feb 07** Name **Ian Renfrew** Page **1** of **2**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
08:55	T/O				take off
9:08	Ascent				Thermogram indicates moist neutral lower atmosphere
	1				inversion at 800mb
	1				Clear skies in general, scattered cloud above.
9:20	1	24 kft			Drop 1 - data straight away. (T from 410mb,
9:23	1 then 2	24 kft			Td from 440mb, WS from 410mb)
9:31	2	"		64N 18W	Drop 1 - hit land ✓
9:35	2	"			Drop 1 - to Hoare (currently queued) → sent 9:46
9:39	2	"			Ozone dropped dramatically.
					Dewpoint consistently above T ?
9:43	2	"			Entered cloud
9:44	2	"		62N 18W	Drop 2 - data straight away. ✓
10:00	2	"			Drop 2 - onto GTS & Drop 2 - sharp inversion 750mb
					Drop 2 - winds at site stronger.
10:06	2	"		60N 18W	Drop 3 - strong str wind 18m/s ✓
10:22	2	"			Drop 3 - onto GTS
10:23	2				Cloud deck below
10:28	2				
10:30	3	27 kft.		58N 18W	Drop 4 - 10 m/s str wind.
10:52	3	25 kft.			Drop 4 - onto GTS, T from 410mb, RH 440, WS 580mb
10:54	4	25 kft		52N 22W	End Run.
10:55	4	"		58N 22W	Drop 5 - 14 m/s low-level wind.
11:08	4				Drop 5 - onto GTS
11:18	4			60N 22W	Drop 6 - 15 m/s low-level wind

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B270 **T/O:** 085519
Date of flight: 24/02/07 **Land:** 144433

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		To Exeter
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B270
Date of Flight: 24/02/07

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	
4) Log on to FLOODS	Y	
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat =
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 59697 Blocks written = 59697 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y	Start = 090000 End = 144500 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Y Are they non-zero in size? Y
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	Y	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images Noise on 2DC towards end. No 2DP data Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 090000 End = 144500 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	Y	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X = A 1 (2DP noise only)</p> <p>Start = 090000 End = 144500</p> <p>Time data processed to = 143149</p> <p>2dproc files present? Y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	Y	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records = 1461, 178</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	Y	<p>X = A Y = (X+1) = B</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	Y	<p>Correlated? Y</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B270
Date of Flight: 24/02/07

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 1.15
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = B Y = X+1 = C
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	Y	Merged OK? Y

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B270	Date	24/02/2007
Page No.	1 of 1	Operator	SWH

GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, splashdown</i>	<i>e.g. windata? PTH data? Lat/Long</i>
092018	1	Launch	392.60 -42.10 72.39 265.50 3.00 - 14.90 -18.009300 64.003000 7317.20
092728	1	Land	896.82 -7.14 36.30 112.79 2.21 - 11.70 -18.024995 63.988215 1275.09
094357	2	Launch	392.30 -43.50 95.78 337.40 3.50 - 14.30 -18.000600 61.995100 7322.30
095248	2	Land	1002.54 2.35 87.77 47.68 17.68 - 10.37 -18.056122 61.965353 99999.00
100651	3	Launch	392.50 -44.40 107.87 263.60 5.90 - 14.20 -17.999800 59.988600 7318.90
101532	3	Land	995.89 5.71 73.47 46.46 15.93 - 11.64 -18.033311 59.967578 356.61
103015	4	Launch	392.00 -41.20 44.60 304.90 8.40 - 15.00 -18.133100 58.001900 7327.20
103846	4	Land	991.67 7.46 85.88 33.23 8.82 - 8.62 -18.113828 57.978113 363.19 8
105518	5	Launch	375.10 -42.70 76.33 311.70 16.10 - 13.90 -21.967800 58.067400 7635.60
110412	5	Land	993.63 7.71 81.46 55.36 13.31 - 11.58 -21.978939 58.041235 364.94
111851	6	Launch	375.90 -45.40 54.41 325.90 10.40 - 13.90 -21.999300 60.022300 7622.40
112740	6	Land	999.16 5.67 63.79 60.91 14.58 - 11.47 -22.034385 59.987977 393.51
114206	7	Launch	375.60 -45.10 62.56 74.60 5.40 - 13.90 -22.002200 61.986200 7626.90
115057	7	Land	1004.20 4.38 58.22 85.64 7.86 - 11.32 -22.017197 61.966283 366.70
121524	8	Launch	359.40 -48.20 102.28 265.70 8.60 - 14.30 -26.062800 63.968600 7934.60
122448	8	Land	1010.30 1.01 57.52 44.82 11.70 - 10.95 -26.093288 63.944175 354.77
123842	9	Launch	359.50 -48.80 80.43 205.60 7.30 - 13.50 -25.999100 61.990800 7931.20
124819	9	Land	1006.57 2.42 53.05 26.37 8.18 - 10.14 -25.989781 61.974262 385.31
130233	10	Launch	359.40 -47.10 23.43 293.80 15.90 - 13.30 -25.999200 59.929900 7934.40
131034	10	Land	1003.54 5.96 69.66 63.77 9.99 - 10.82 -25.997526 59.971117 366.94
132333	11	Launch	359.50 -45.40 79.24 303.00 11.90 - 12.80 -25.991300 57.994100 7932.10
133253	11	Land	998.22 7.05 83.24 71.96 14.02 - 11.92 -26.003835 57.972550 324.93

Flight:

B270

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

**Report Created 15/03/2007
12:11:36**

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

25/02/2007

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B270

Date: 24 Feb 2007

Instruments

1. FFC window dirty
2. CO – suspect initial cal, only got up to around 300ppb
3. Heimann calcs don't work at altitude – too cold for the peltier to control the temp?

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 24/2/07

Flight No: 270

Pre-Flighter: BW

<u>Item</u>	<u>✓ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	Topped up De-ionised water supply
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	Restart Not on internal disk to log
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	Cal Gas Pressure 5.17 bar
17	<input type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	
18	<input type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	Video refilled before flight.
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			

External Checks overleaf →

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u> <input type="checkbox"/> or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>			
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	_____
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JW	Cleaned & Checked	_____
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	_____
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	_____
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	_____
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> GE	Cleaned & Checked	_____
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	_____
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Camera Windows	Cleaned	_____
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Heimann	Lens checked OK	_____
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TWC Cover	Fitted if required	_____
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All other covers	Removed	_____
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Dustbin	Returned to hangar	_____
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	_____
42	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Avalon informed	_____
<u>Avalon Checks</u>			Signed
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		_____
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ICEX applied		_____
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Traps empty (weekly only)		_____

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B270:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	No In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	20 Mar 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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Daily weather summary 24 February 2007

<p>Large scale situation today:</p>	<p>3 cyclones extend across the Atlantic. The largest is off the coast of Newfoundland with 976hPa centre pressure. A 988 hPa low is southeast of the tip of Greenland and is heading east into the last of the three which is north of Ireland. The mesoscale cyclone has moved to 70N 00E and has deepened to 999hPa. In the upper levels there is a high pressure centre sitting over Greenland and a trough extending from the mesoscale cyclone over Iceland. (Based on UKMO 00Z)</p>
<p>Features of interest:</p>	<p>There are no a lot of interesting meteorological features within the range of the aircraft. There are some indications of acceleration of surface winds by the Cape Farewell.</p> <div data-bbox="363 689 1358 1406" style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> <p style="text-align: center;">Analysis chart valid 00 UTC Sat 24 FEB 2007</p> </div>
<p>Action:</p>	<p>A targeting flight to the south of Iceland.</p>
<p>Outlook for the next 24-48 hours:</p>	<p>The mesoscale cyclone is quasi-stationary around 70N 5W while the low over the UK drifts slowly into Denmark. The second low moves close to the large cyclone off the coast of Newfoundland and then around it towards the tip of Greenland. By the end of two days, the flow upstream of Iceland is from the north, there is flow splitting around the island with most of the air flowing by the east coast (influenced by the Coriolis force), creating a significant wake to the south.</p>
<p>Outlook for the next 48-96 hours:</p>	<p>The mesoscale cyclone begins to dissipate and has disappeared after 84hrs. The low to the south of Greenland extends a trough eastward in which two cyclones form. The first is to the west of Iceland and merges with the parent cyclone. The second forms north of Ireland and deepens to 965hPa over Scotland. This low is shown with two cores in the ECMWF. Interestingly, the 96hr forecast in both models shows a continuous trough connecting the mesoscale cyclone, the low over Scotland and the low to the south of Greenland.</p>